

8T – Weaknesses in the QFT Framework

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Abstract:

By analyzing the ideas, main equations and methods within the QFT framework, it becomes vividly clear that there are weaknesses in certain domains. From doing the space-time integral, which is not possible for more than one reason, to the description of minimal vacuum state as a set of zeros, to the complexity of notation which makes nature, which in essence is quite simple, hard to grasp.

Introduction

First, we can represent the QFT functional integral, equation (1) that we cannot solve.

$$Z = \int D\varphi e^{i \int d^4x [\frac{1}{2}\partial\varphi^2 - V(\varphi) + J(x)\varphi(x)]} \quad (1)$$

The QFT framework is assuming such a thing is solvable and we can not solve it. Author will argue it is incorrect. First, by integrating all over space-time, physicists make an implicit assumption that space-time is continuous and smooth. Such an assumption is invalid, in the new 8T framework in which space-time is the matric tensor varying presented in equation (2), there could be knots, deformations of the matric tensor to the flow, i.e. the base space, given by fiber bundle.

$$\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

So already, it is the first complication on the QFT framework, which count as a weakness. The second, QFT classify notions according to fields, which is a function of space-time, at the same time it lacks providing reasoning to what those fields are, or how they were created. QFT domain of description does not include dark energy, dark matter, the moment of singularity, gravity and curvature. Its domain of description is mainly partial and limited, despite its accuracy. Another point which is quite important is that in examining a theory we should classify according to two different categories. The first, is the ideas, equations and predictions. the second is the methods in which those ideas are described. For example, invariance under shifting frames in quantum scale is described by group theory suggested by Wigner in 1930. If we classify QFT according to ideas and methods, it is vividly clear that there are few simple ideas described by complicated methods and long and unclear notation.

Take for example the so-called, vacuum that is described by a set of elements as given in equation (3):

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^K |0_i \tag{3}$$

So the description of the vacuum is made by a discrete set of elements that the relation among them is unclear. In addition, implies that they are all the same. A collection of zeros, which is, according to QFT, does not mean that the vacuum is empty. That is another weakness as the state of minima can be described by better means as one believes. The vacuum is the matrix tensor, in areas where there are no arbitrary variations created as presented in equation (3.1).

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = \emptyset \tag{3.1}$$

The vacuum is than varying in position along the matrix tensor, it than implies that there could be several vacuums at the same time across the matrix tensor, they could vanish and reborn, grow or decay. Such a framework makes it easy to understand and grasp the ideas presented in QFT in a better and easier fashion. Another weakness is that it only describes three interactions, strong weak and the electro-magnetic, while it should be able to predict and describe an infinite series of interactions, which are net curvature on the manifold. Scientists working on QFT searched for a way to unify gravity with QM. To our great surprise all, the numbers of QM raise from elevated framework of GR. In other words, QM is not unified, it was derived. It was indeed Einstein last triumph.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{3.2}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{3.21}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{3.3}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{3.31}$$

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)